

A guide to selecting high-performing renewable antibodies for SCARB2 across western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence

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Abstract

Scavenger receptor class B member 2 (SCARB2), also known as lysosomal integral membrane protein type 2 (LIMP-2), is a multifunctional glycoprotein critical for lysosomal biogenesis and neuronal homeostasis. We characterized twelve commercially antibodies against SCARB2 in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and ten in immunofluorescence using a standardized workflow. Antibody performance was assessed by comparing signals in a wild-type cell line and its corresponding knockout derivative. This work is part of a broader collaborative public-good initiative to improve biomedical research by systematically evaluating commercial antibodies against human proteins and openly sharing the data as a resource for the scientific community. We encourage readers to use this report as a guide for selecting antibodies best suited to their specific applications.

Keywords:

UniProt ID Q14108, SCARB2, SCARB2, lysosomal integral membrane protein 2, LIMP II, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

SCARB2 serves as a receptor for the lysosomal enzyme β -glucocerebrosidase (GCase), mediating its trafficking from the endoplasmic reticulum to lysosomes (1). Dysfunction of this pathway contributes to the accumulation of glycolipids and lysosomal stress, mechanisms strongly implicated in neurodegenerative disorders such as Parkinson's disease (PD) and action myoclonus–renal failure (AMRF) syndrome (2, 3).

Here, we characterized twelve antibodies against SCARB2, for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using standardized protocols. Antibody performance was assessed by comparing signal in wild-type (WT) and knockout (KO) cell lines. The resulting data can guide the selection of antibodies best suited to specific research needs, enabling robust biochemical and cellular assessment of the target.

This work is part of a broader collaborative initiative involving academics, funders, and antibody manufacturers, aimed at improving biomedical research reproducibility through the systematic characterization of commercial antibodies against human proteins and open data sharing. Antibodies are provided in-kind by participating manufacturers. The approach involves identifying cell lines with sufficient target expression, generating or sourcing corresponding KO cell lines, and evaluating commercially available antibodies, with a focus on renewable (monoclonal and recombinant) reagents (4). We do not provide explicit antibody recommendations; rather, the data are presented to enable independent interpretation. Guidance on data interpretation is available via the YCharOS gateway (5) and in Table 5 of this data note.

Results and discussion

Antibody performance was assessed by comparing readouts from WT and KO cells (4). The first step is to identify a cell line expressing sufficient levels of the target protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap transcriptomics database (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) to identify cell lines with expression levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), a threshold we have found to be suitable (6). The MCF7 cell line expresses the *SCARB2* transcript at $7.2 \log_2(\text{TPM}+1)$, and a corresponding *SCARB2* KO MCF7 cell line was obtained from Abcam (Table 1). Moreover, as seen on DepMap, the MCF7 does not carry mutations in the *SCARB2* gene that could affect antibody-epitope binding.

Primary antibodies are listed in Table 2, with usage conditions summarized in Table 3 and secondary antibodies in Table 4. Antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios to align with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations.

All twelve antibodies were first tested in western blot using WT and *SCARB2* KO protein lysates (Figure 1). This step enables concurrent validation of the KO cell line (absence of detectable *SCARB2* signal) and identification of antibodies that detect *SCARB2* with a band that is absent in the KO lane. Dilutions were selected based on supplier recommendations and adjusted when necessary (Table 3).

The ability of each antibody to capture SCARB2 from MCF7 lysates was assessed by immunoprecipitation followed by western blot analysis (Figure 2). Each immunoprecipitation was performed using 2 µg of antibody, or 5 µL when the concentration was not available (Table 3). Starting material (SM), unbound (UB), and immunoprecipitated (IP) fractions were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and probed using antibody 702770 identified in the western blot screen. This assay evaluates target capture but does not assess selectivity (i.e., binding to SCARB2 versus off-target proteins).

For immunofluorescence, ten recombinant antibodies were screened at two dilutions using a mosaic strategy in which WT and KO cells, pre-labelled with distinct dyes, were imaged within the same field of view to minimize experimental bias (Figure 3). Antibodies were tested at supplier-recommended dilutions when available; otherwise, they were tested at 1 and 2 µg/mL (Table 3). Because detergent choice can strongly influence staining of lysosomal proteins (7), both saponin and Triton X-100 were evaluated.

Signal was quantified across at least 500 WT and KO cells (4), and representative images are shown in Figure 3. For each antibody, the WT/KO signal intensity ratio is reported: values near 1 indicate comparable signal in WT and KO cells, values >1 indicate enrichment in WT cells, and values <1 indicate higher signal in KO cells. The value shown corresponds to the condition yielding the highest ratio. These ratios facilitate comparison under the conditions tested but should be interpreted within the context of the specific assay and cell type.

In conclusion, we screened twelve SCARB2 commercial antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and ten antibodies by immunofluorescence by comparing signal in WT and SCARB2 KO MCF7 cell lines. To assist with data interpretation, Table 5 outlines common antibody performance scenarios across applications. High-quality renewable antibodies detecting SCARB2 were identified for each application. Researchers studying SCARB2 in other species are encouraged to consider these results and verify predicted species reactivity with the manufacturer before proceeding.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. First, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all available antibodies against any given targets. While YCharOS partners provide access to the majority of renewable antibodies, some widely used polyclonal antibodies may not be included.

Second, the YCharOS approach is protein-agnostic and aims to provide objective data on antibody performance without predefined expectations regarding molecular weight or localization. As such, only a brief overview of the protein target is provided, and expert interpretation of banding patterns and subcellular localization is encouraged.

Third, experiments are not performed in biological replicates due to the parallel testing of multiple antibodies recognizing distinct epitopes. The identification of at least one specific antibody supports target expression in WT cells and its absence in KO cells, providing a reference for evaluating other antibodies. Experiments are performed using standardized conditions and master mixes to minimize variability. In immunofluorescence, testing at multiple antibody concentrations provides an additional assessment of specificity. Experiments may be repeated when no signal is detected. Furthermore, these data are generated independently of manufacturers' validation processes, effectively constituting an external replication.

Finally, conclusions are limited to the experimental conditions and cell line used. The reliance on a single cell type represents a constraint, as protein expression levels can influence antibody performance. The use of cancer cell lines also introduces potential confounders, including mutations that may affect antibody-epitope binding. These limitations are inherent to cell line-based validation approaches.

Method

The standardized protocols used for this antibody characterization study were established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers, and antibody manufacturers (4). Brief descriptions of the experimental procedures used in this study are described below.

Cell lines

The cell lines used in this study are listed in Table 1. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (8). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Primary and secondary antibodies

Primary antibodies are listed in Table 2 with RRIDs (9). Working dilutions for western blot and immunofluorescence, and volumes corresponding to 2 µg input for immunoprecipitation, are provided in Table 3. Secondary antibodies and their working concentrations are listed in Table 4. Antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios.

Antibody screening by western blot

MCF7 WT and *SCARB2* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C and 30 µg of protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for rat antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

MCF7 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 1 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

MCF7 WT and *SCARB2* KO cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain. WT and KO cells were plated on 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Culture medium was removed, and cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL) for 10 min at room temperature. Cells were permeabilized in PBS1x with 0.05% Saponin (MilliporeSigma, cat. number 47036) or 0.1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature. Cells were blocked in IF buffer (PBS1x with 5% BSA and 0.005% Saponin or 0.01% Triton X-100) with 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) for 1 h at room temperature. Cells were incubated with the corresponding IF buffer containing the primary *SCARB2* antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with the corresponding Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibody in IF buffer for 1 hr at room temperature. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with PBS1x then incubated with DAPI and washed once with PBS1x.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.94 air objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. A minimum of 500 WT and KO cells were imaged per antibody. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification (10). We have developed a collection of scripts in Python and in ImageJ/FIJI

made openly available on GitHub (https://github.com/ABIF-McGill/YCharOS_IF_characterization) (4).
Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Data availability

Underlying data

Dataset for the SCARB2 antibody screening study: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18805484.

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab271144	CVCL_0031	MCF7	WT
Abcam	ab274952	CVCL_B9BE	MCF7	SCARB2 KO

Table 2: Summary of the SCARB2 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab176317**	1068975-2	AB_2620169	recombinant mono	EPR12080	rabbit	0.10	Wb, IP
Abcam	ab196651**	GR312647-3	AB_3101952	recombinant mono	EPR12081	rabbit	0.84	Wb
Abcam	ab314217**	1065721-4	AB_3101784	recombinant mono	EPR26243-125	rabbit	0.53	Wb, IP, IF
ABclonal	A9185**	4000001467	AB_2863681	recombinant mono	ARC1467	rabbit	0.24	Wb
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB1888*	JUZ024071	AB_2182970	monoclonal	220411	rat	1.00	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP3-22186**	240465	AB_3097844	recombinant mono	SR2211	rabbit	NA	Wb, IP
Cell Signaling Technology	27960**	1	AB_3083079	recombinant mono	E2Z5F	rabbit	0.33	Wb, IP, IF
Proteintech	27102-1-AP	00050639	AB_2880756	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	702770**	2477085	AB_2723321	recombinant mono	12H5L1	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	703037**	2942968	AB_2734813	recombinant mono	22H6L14	rabbit	0.50	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	711805**	2384977	AB_2723322	recombinant poly	12HCLC	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	712072**	2854061	AB_2724602	recombinant poly	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Dilutions of SCARB2 antibodies used in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Catalog number	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendor-recommended Wb dilution	Wb dilution used	IP volume (µL, for 2 µg input)	Vendor-recommended IF dilution	IF dilution tested (1)	IF dilution tested (2)	IF dilution shown
ab176317**	0.10	1/1000 - 1/5000	1/1000	20.2	-	1/10	1/100	1/100
ab196651**	0.84	1/20000	1/20000	2.4	1/100	1/100	1/800	1/800
ab314217**	0.53	1/1000	1/1000	3.8	1/50	1/50	1/500	1/50
A9185**	0.24	1/500 – 1/1000	1/500	8.3	-	1/200	1/500	1/200
MAB1888*	1.00	1/1000	1/1000	2.0	-	-	-	-
NBP3-22186**	-	1/500 – 1/2000	1/500	5.0	-	1/200	1/500	1/200
27960**	0.33	1/1000	1/200	6.1	1/50 – 1/100	1/100	1/300	1/300
27102-1-AP	0.50	1/1000 – 1/8000	1/1000	4.0	-	-	-	-
702770**	0.50	1/500	1/500	4.0	-	1/250	1/500	1/500
703037**	0.50	1/1000	1/1000	4.0	1/100	1/100	1/500	1/500
711805**	0.50	1/200	1/200	4.0	-	1/250	1/500	1/500
712072**	0.50	1/1000	1/1000	4.0	1/100	1/100	1/500	1/500

Table 4: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Invitrogen	HRP-Goat Anti-Rat Antibody (H+L)	31470	AB_228356	polyclonal	0.8	0.4
Cell Signaling Technology	Protein A, HRP conjugate	12291	NA	polyclonal	0.125	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR003	AB_3073507	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5
Invitrogen	Alexa Fluor™ 555-Goat anti-Rat (H+L)	A-21434	AB_141733	polyclonal	2	0.5

Table 5: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Western blot			Immunoprecipitation			Immunofluorescence		
<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>Target protein detected (arrowhead)</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>Target protein detected (arrowhead) among others</p>	<p>Unsuccessful antibody</p> <p>Target protein not detected</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>Target protein captured in the IP</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>Target protein captured in the IP</p>	<p>Unsuccessful antibody</p> <p>Target protein not captured in the IP</p>	<p>WT/KO cell mosaic</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>Target protein detected (white staining)</p>	<p>Unsuccessful antibody</p> <p>Target protein not detected</p>

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Figure 1: SCARB2 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: SCARB2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: SCARB2 antibody screening by immunofluorescence (1/2)

Figure 3: SCARB2 antibody screening by immunofluorescence (2/2)

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: SCARB2 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates from MCF7 WT and SCARB2 KO were prepared and analyzed in western blot using the indicated SCARB2 antibodies. Ponceau-stained membranes are shown to confirm equal loading and efficient protein transfer from gel to membrane. Predicted molecular weight: 54 kDa. ** = recombinant antibody; * = monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: SCARB2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

MCF7 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using the indicated SCARB2 antibodies. Immunoprecipitates were analyzed by western blot using SCARB2 antibody 702770** (1/500). Ponceau-stained membranes are shown. SM = 6% starting material; UB = 6% unbound fraction; IP = immunoprecipitate. ** = recombinant antibody; * = monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: SCARB2 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

MCF7 WT and SCARB2 KO cells were pre-labelled with green and far-red fluorescent dyes, respectively, mixed at a 1:1 ratio, and plated in 96-well plates. Cells were permeabilized with saponin or Triton X-100 and stained with the indicated SCARB2 antibodies. Representative images of the antibody and DAPI channels (grayscale) are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed lines, respectively. WT/KO signal intensity ratios are indicated in the top-left corner of each antibody channel image. Scale bar = 10 μ m. ** = recombinant antibody; * = monoclonal antibody.